

Research Paper

**Reclaiming Sexual Empowerment after Surviving Childhood Sexual Abuse from the
experience of therapists in private practice in Ireland.**

By

Anita Lynch

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Title Reclaiming sexual empowerment after surviving childhood sexual abuse from the experience of therapists in private practice in Ireland.

Abstract

This paper is about reclaiming sexual empowerment after surviving childhood sexual abuse from the lens of therapists in an Irish therapeutic setting. There is much documented about the effects of childhood sexual abuse on adult's sexuality and sexual dysfunction. However, there is no literature on reclaiming sexual empowerment after surviving childhood sexual abuse in an Irish therapeutic setting. Furthermore, the topic of sex and childhood sexual abuse is still not commonly spoken about in the therapy room. This qualitative piece of research interviewed six Irish psychotherapists to explore why this area of recovery for survivors is not frequently being addressed in the therapy room of private practitioners. The findings of this study revealed; that there is a lack of training around childhood sexual abuse, the Irish culture, particularly the influence of the Catholic church and not being comfortable to openly talk about sex, the therapists own fears/bias, and that childhood sexual abuse is still a taboo, are some of the huge barriers as to why the survivor and therapist are not addressing reclaiming sexual empowerment in recovery from childhood sexual abuse.

Introduction

This paper will explore from the therapists' experience who work with adult survivors of childhood sexual abuse from the aspect of reclaiming their sexual empowerment. It will examine some of the topics around barriers, benefits and meaning both clients and therapists attribute to this area, from the perspective of the Irish therapist in private practice. It will begin with brief definitions of the concepts, a literature review, the metological scope of the research, and conclude with showcasing the findings and followed by a discussion.

Definitions

Childhood Sexual Abuse

According to the World Health Organization, (1999); Gewirtz-Meydon & Fir-Lovee, (2021), Childhood sexual abuse (CSA) is defined as:

- the involvement of a child in sexual activity that they do not fully understand, are unable to give informed consent to, are not developmentally ready for and or that violates social norms or legal restrictions.
- CSA is demonstrated by sexual activity between a child and an adult/another child who, because to their age or stage of development, is in a position of trust, power, or responsibility, which is for the sexual gratification of the other person.
- This may include, but is not limited to, forcing, or coercing a child into any sexual action, including prostitution, pornography or other sexual activities.

Sexuality

Hawkins, Cornwall & Lewin (2011) state, an essential component of our well-being is sexuality. They go on to say our sexualities, sexual preferences, and sexual experiences determine who we are. These factors can also have a big impact on our health, prosperity, happiness, and ability to contribute to our communities and societies.

Hawkins, Cornwall & Lewin, (2011) claim, it's common to misunderstand the word "sexuality", because of this, it may be challenging to understand how women's empowerment and sexuality are intimately related, stating sexuality encompasses more than just sexual orientation or preference.

Sexual Empowerment

The ability to understand and exert influence over one's own personal, social, political, and economic forces to take action or change one's behaviour in order to better one's living conditions, including one's health, is known as empowerment (Israel et al., 1994; Parker et al., 2002).

Sexual empowerment is understood as psychosocial process that assists people in making decisions about their sexuality, such as rejecting unwanted habits and promoting sexual desires (Grose et al., 2020; Peterson, 2010). Sexual empowerment research has aimed to increase people's confidence in their ability to exercise personal agency and engage in safer sexual activities (Hightow-Weidman et al., 2018).

Aim

The aim of this research is to establish what the barriers are for adult survivors of CSA in reclaiming their sexual empowerment in a therapeutic setting as viewed through the lens of psychotherapists in private practice in Ireland.

Objectives

The objectives of this research are:

1. To gain an understanding of how CSA impacts survivors' sexuality.
2. To examine what the barriers and benefits for survivors in reclaiming their sexual empowerment in a therapeutic setting.
3. To explore what are the barriers and benefits for therapists in helping survivors, reclaim their sexual empowerment.
4. To establish if reclaiming their sexual empowerment is important to survivors, and their recovery process. If not, why not?
5. To determine what meaning survivors, make of reclaiming their sexual empowerment after surviving CSA.

Rationale

After trawling an extensive literature review, this author discovered a gap in the research on reclaiming sexual empowerment in survivors of CSA from an Irish therapeutic perspective. There is a plethora of research on CSA, particularly in the past eighteen months after covid, where researchers systematically reviewed published articles, to discover what emerges, however, these were heavily relied upon student data from Western Countries (McCarthy-Jones, 2021). This author is passionate about working with survivors of CSA. This is rooted in an intergenerational family history of CSA. A positive experience of attending the Rape Crisis Centre sparked a drive to become qualified as a psychotherapist. After gaining valuable diverse experience abroad, this author returned home to discover many therapists and survivors are not talking about sexual empowerment healing. The hope for this study is to add a valuable contribution to research in terms of improving survivors' experiences in an Irish therapeutic setting.

Literature Review

Irish history tells a story of poverty and colonization, which has led to a sense of hopelessness and emotional suppression, for more than a century. (O'Morain, McAuliffe, Conroy, Johnson & Michel, 2012). Up until the 1960s, most Irish people had a comprehensive set of rules for behaviour and thought dictated by Catholicism. One theory for why counselling wasn't widely known until the 1970s and 1980s is the impact of religion (Chamberlain, 1983). Irish attitudes on sex, religion, emotional expression, and authority have drastically changed more recently as a result of modernism's influence in the country, these topics are crucial for counselling (O'Morain, McAuliffe, Conroy, Johnson & Michel, 2012).

Until the late 1990s, a considerable number of people in Ireland were victims of well-documented clerical and institutional abuses (Hyland, Vallières, Cloitre, BenEzra, Karatzias, Olf, Murphy & Shevlin, 2020). Statistics for counselling show that 19.84% of presentations were for religious/clerical abuse and 34.5% was for familial/ex familial abuse (One in Four Charity 2021).

Numerous studies have demonstrated that the effects of CSA an adult sexuality are likely to be severely detrimental (Kendall-Tackett, Williams, & Finkelhor, 1993; Noll, Trickett, & Putnam, 2003; Nurcombe, 2000). More than any other type of childhood trauma, CSA is believed to have an impact on an adult's sexual health and is linked to greater sexual dysfunction and lower sexual satisfaction as an adult, as well as to higher degrees of sexual compulsivity and sexual risk behaviours, according to research published over the past ten years. (Bigras, Vaillancourt-Morel, Nolin & Bergeron, 2020).

In Ireland, the SAVI report revealed that 30% of women and 24% of men experienced some form of sexual abuse before the age of 17 (McGee et.al. 2002). Researchers and clinicians need a better grasp in understanding the impact this widespread problem has on survivors' lives (Fergusson, McLeod, & Horwood, 2013; Johnson et al, 2019).

Træen & Sørensen (2008) argue that the most challenging aspect of healing from trauma may be reclaiming a stolen body, as the wound won't mend on its own. Survivors were discovered to be more inclined to view their bodies as a source of suffering as opposed to a source of sexual pleasure (Godbout, Bakhos, Dussault, and Hebert, 2020). The desire for sexual

pleasure is likely to be suppressed by feelings of shame and intimacy issues are more likely to be closely related to abuse (Coleman, Rosser, & Strapko, 1992; Træen & Sørensen, 2008).

Maltz (2002) states sexual healing is a liberating process that enables survivors to deal with and resolve sexual issues brought on by prior trauma. It entails deliberately changing sexual attitudes and behaviours using specific strategies and technique (Maltz, 2002). However, Love & Faber (2017) state that discussing sex and sexuality in therapy is typically challenging and complex for both clients and therapists. Hawkins, Cornwall and Lewin, (2011), argue that the most private and intimate part of who we are is our sexuality. They warn therapists not to ignore or further marginalise survivors whose concept of sexual empowerment might be different to their own. Therapists play a crucial role in assisting survivors understand sexual difficulties in creative and positive ways by being educated on sexual abuse and sexual healing practice (Bigras, Vaillancourt-Morel, Nolin & Bergeron, 2020).

Recent studies have shown that far from being rendered permanently crippled by their experiences, many adult CSA survivors are able to heal and move forward with their lives, leading full and satisfying lives (Vilenica, Shakespeare-Finch & Obst, 2013). The majority of earlier research on CSA centred on female survivors. This makes it challenging to determine the prevalence of CSA among men due to under-reporting (Winder, 1996). In our society, silence is a symbol of powerlessness, so, it is understandable that victims of rape frequently keep their experiences a secret (George, Winfeld, & Blazer, 1992; Koss, 1985; McAuslan, 1998; Ahrens 2006).

Meaning-making seems to be a crucial aspect of recovery and development following this trauma (Park, 2010; Vilenica, Shakespeare-Finch & Obst, 2013). Therapists can educate survivors about strategies and interventions as well as making choices to reduce negative transference (Maltz, 2002). Wheeler (2000) stated for a therapist to be effective and competent, it has nothing to do with the therapeutic approach they use.

Methodology

This author has opted for a qualitative methodology to understand the reclaiming of sexual empowerment and personal experiences of survivors of CSA from the experiences of therapists. Prosman, Lo Fo Wong, and Lagro-Janssen (2013) claim qualitative research methods are preferable when seeking to comprehend the needs of abused women. Dornan &

Kelly (2016) state clinical professionals can better manage doubts and ambiguities using narrative information than with paradigmatic knowledge. Clarifying cause-and-effect linkages is how qualitative research has an impact in changing clinical practice and assist therapists in their decision making (Dornan & Kelly, 2016).

1.1 Data Analysis and Interpretation

The data was analysed by interpretive phenomenological analysis (IPA). A variety of fields, most notably the health sciences, have adopted this relatively new methodological technique, which has its roots in psychology (Oxley, 2016). IPA researchers work to develop an understanding of how people experience significant life events by examining how people make meaning of their life experiences. Since it is difficult to convert experiences into quantifiable data and a lot would be lost in the process, IPA is firmly rooted in qualitative research. (Oxley, 2016).

A phenomenological epistemology is married to IPA, which prioritizes experience, it focuses on deeply comprehending how individuals actually experience reality on a daily basis in order to comprehend the issue at hand (Bruan & Clarke, 2006).

1.2 Bias

This research is different than quantitative research, where the objective is to remove bias using objective measurements like tests, organized interviews, or questionnaires. Such objectivity, according to a qualitative researchers, is impossible (Kisely, & Kendall, 2011). It is important to disclose this author works in the area of CSA with adult survivors and is also a survivor of CSA.

1.3 Data Collection

Data was collected from the participants using semi-structured interviews consisting of ten questions from the objectives outlined (See Appendix A). Interviews were conducted online using zoom and lasted approximately 25 to 40 minutes. Interviews were recorded and transcribed. All recordings and transcriptions will be deleted following completion of the master's award. Participants were given a research pack, which consisted of a consent form, an information sheet, welcome letter, demographics questionnaire and a debriefing sheet.

These were sent by email to each participant. A copy of the information pack is in (Appendix B).

Individual semi-structured interviews are frequently used in (IPA) studies as they give participants the chance to provide rich and thorough explanations of their opinions and experiences (Oxley, 2016). Semi-structured interviews are best because they give the researcher a framework but also let the participant lead the conversation by allowing questions to be adjusted or dropped in response to the participant's account. For an IPA study, this is crucial because the researcher wants the participant to discuss the parts of their experience that are meaningful to them (Oxley, 2016).

1.4 The Participants

Six participants responded to an advertisement which was posted on social media groups for counsellors/psychotherapists and on the authors own social media platforms. However, there was exclusion criteria for professional and ethical safety. The inclusion/exclusion criteria are set out in Table 1 below.

Table 1:

Parameters	Inclusion Criteria	Exclusion Criteria
Language	English speaking	Non-English speaking
Location	Ireland	Outside of Ireland
Population	Qualified therapist	Students
Ethical	Membership of governing body	No membership
Access	Working with client survivors of CSA	Not working with client survivors of CSA
Environment	Working in private practice in Ireland	Not working in private practice in Ireland
Supervision	Attending regular supervision	No Supervisory process

1.5 Demographics

All participants interviewed were Irish and female. One participant was divorced and the other five were married with an average of two children each ranging from primary to secondary school. Participants ages ranged within 35 to 55 years old. One participant was qualified 1.5 years and the other five participants ranged from 10 to 17 years qualified and

working in private practice over 10 years. Their modalities ranged from Person -Centred, Psychodynamic, Integrative, Adlerian and Eye Movement Desensitization and Reprocessing.

1.6 Ethical Considerations

Although the participants are qualified psychotherapists, consideration was given that they may be survivors of CSA, therefore it was imperative that the researcher was sensitive to the questions being asked and how they might trigger the participant. At the beginning of each interview, the researcher outlined the sensitive content of the topic and reassured the participant of the right to skip a question or end the recording at any time. Safety of the participant was of the upmost concern for the researcher. Again, at the end of each interview, the researcher provided an opportunity to debrief with each participant off camera. All therapists are required to attend regular supervision as per the code of ethics of the governing bodies in Ireland. When research participants are only minimally at risk, it is seen ethically unproblematic (Smythe & Murray, 2000).

This author was committed to protecting the participants personal information by use of anonymity by keeping all identifiable information confidential. Participants names are changed and referred to by alphabetical letters (Smythe & Murray, 2000).

Findings

Each participant, in interview was asked to describe their understanding of CSA, sexuality and sexual empowerment. Their responses were consistent and similar language was used in their explanations. However, one participant said:

“ultimately I think when children are sexually abused, it’s not just sexual abuse, it’s nearly the rape of their soul...because of the long-term impact and the damage that it does to their whole psyche” Pt. C.

The participants voiced many reasons as to the barriers to clients reclaiming their sexual empowerment. The main themes identified, that were mentioned by all six participants following these interviews using the IPA process were; the Irish Culture, the Irish Therapist and the lack of Training in Ireland. Table 2 shows the themes identified using the IPA process, the colour coding used can be seen in a copy of one of the transcripts in Appendix C.

Table 2:

Main Theme 1	Main Theme 2
<p><i>Impact on Sexuality:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Differences. 	<p><i>The Irish Culture:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It's a taboo. • Can't talk about it. • Religious Background
Main Theme 3	Main Theme 4
<p><i>The Irish Therapist:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Can't talk about it. • Inexperienced. • Biases and judgements. 	<p><i>The Irish Training:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gap in training. • Specialized training.
Main Theme 5	
<p><i>Meaning Making:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Is RSE important to clients. 	

Theme 1- Impact on sexuality

The life experience of the participants lends richness to the study. Of the six participants interviewed, three disclosed that they were survivors of CSA, two more did not comment on their position, although stated they specialize in this area and the final one admitted that they had no personal experience of abuse. Each participant was asked how CSA impacts a client's sexuality;

. . . *“if they are male and they’ve been sexually abused by another man....they often wonder is that because...is that why I’m gay.... it’s very normal to be confused anyway about sexuality but it’s actually heart breaking....in a very complex way” Pt. C.*

. . . *“I think very negatively.... He was abused by a male, and it has made him very insecure of his body” Pt. S.*

Dimock (1988), identified "masculine identity confusion" which is a product of men's socialization and development. He further held that there are two types of masculine confusion: confusion over sexual preferences and confusion about traditional male duties which is upheld by Winder (1996).

One participant acknowledged the differences based on the gender;

“For males, the clients that I work with...there’s a real prevalence of increase in sexual acting out and the use of pornography...for the female clients that I have, their experiences of sexual abuse... they have detached from their sexual self” Pt. O.

For another, it was the interruption that led to a dysfunctional connection to their client’s sexuality;

“the dysfunctional connection that’s made when there’s a sexual abuse or a sexual act to a minor, then there’s a disconnect of what sexuality is.....that connection is.... badly formed... Interrupted” Pt. Y

Disclosure of being a survivor of CSA illuminated how views on sexuality are skewed;

“thinking about the cases I’ve had, or even thinking about my own experience of childhood sexual abuse, I’d say that it definitely, can make things a lot more difficult for you in life....my view of sex and sexuality.... was very skewed” Pt. L.

The final participant, who had no personal history of CSA, stated that clients can have a healthy relationship with their sexuality despite the experience of abuse;

“Sometimes it doesn’t impact a person’s sexuality. Sometimes it does. Many people who have experienced childhood sexual abuse have very healthy sexual relationships and a very healthy relationship with their sexuality” Pt. H.

Theme 2 - The Irish Culture

The Irish culture was a recurring theme in the interviews when it came to barriers to reclaiming sexual empowerment. The participants all expressed their belief that CSA is still a taboo subject for the majority of Irish people.

2.1 Taboo Topic

According to Akerlof (1976), a sexual taboo is a societal norm on sexuality that is fervently held and strictly maintained. (Mooijman & Van Dijk, 2014)

“It is to do with culture but there is a whole taboo about sex still. There is a taboo about anything to do with sex and I think child abuse is one of those things. It is so debased and it is so wrong that people can’t comprehend that it happened” Pt. S.

“fear of broaching that taboo subject....there's a lot of shame around sex, sexuality, fantasies, in Ireland” Pt. C.

“is such a taboo subject unfortunately still in this day and age” Pt. L.

Mooijman & Van Dijk, (2014) argue, one would expect society to be accommodating of other people's sexual behaviour as long as no one is harmed and no rights are abused, however, individuals regularly object to sexual behaviour that is innocent and that they view as taboo.

“any person like me or same generation as me or educated in the same way as me.. they will have a barrier to discussion, empowerment, expression” Pt. H.

“there really is a gap in the understanding of sexual abuse...nearly a taboo in themselves.” Pt. S.

2.2 Catholic Background

Four participants discussed how growing up under the influence of the Catholic church led to oppression and shame about sex and sexuality. Particularly in the area of sexuality, the Irish Catholic Church was opposed to any encroachments on family life (Chamberlain, 1983).

“I come from a very strict Catholic background...being an Irish citizen..is a big barrier....there’s a lot of shame around sexuality, especially for women.. no sex outside marriage....we certainly don’t talk about what we do in it” Pt. L.

“plays a huge part, huge” Pt. O.

“I’m not religious.... I would be more open about sexuality and our sex lives and everything like this”Pt. Y

“I’m Irish, I was raised a Catholic, I was educated by nuns, I have two parents....who have all the classic hallmarks of their generation in relation to sex in terms of being oppressed and seeing it as something of shame” Pt. H.

According to Pulverman and Meston (2020), sexual shame, is defined as shame relating to one's past sexual experiences and acts, that has a strong and significant association with CSA.

2.3 Irish people are not comfortable to talk about sex

Almost every element of our lives is impacted by sex, it can be a source of fulfilment or conflict, an intimate deed or one tinged with shame (Love & Faber, 2017). However, five of the participants stated Irish people are not at all comfortable talking about sex;

“Irish people aren’t good about talking about sex and relationships. We don’t even talk about pornography so there’s a huge cultural barrier there” Pt. O

“because of the way we are in Ireland, we’re very closed around the topic of sex and indeed sexual empowerment” Pt. L

“we are not good at talking about sex in Ireland....“women won’t talk about it with their own women’s group” Pt. Y

“we don’t talk about sex anyway in this country” Pt. S

Theme 3 - The Irish Therapist

One of the strongest themes to emerge was about the Irish therapist in terms of not being comfortable to talk about sex, CSA and their fears, bias and judgements when counselling clients.

3.1 The Irish Therapist not comfortable to talk about sex

For both clients and therapists, discussing sex and sexuality in therapy is frequently a difficult task. (Love & Faber, 2017).

“Nobody talks about sex in this country, that transfers into the professional world and its awful that therapistsalthough you go for your training and you learn to talk about stuff, it is still a subject that is very difficult for people to broach” Pt. S

“the Irish therapists I would say in particular, are very afraid to touch this subject, because they actually don’t know how to cope with it themselves” Pt. L

“how comfortable is the therapist to sit and talk to clients about pornography, masturbation, ejaculation, just the basic things, sexual basics” Pt. O

Finlay (2012) argues that sex is a typical cause of problems and a part of life. While discussing sex is widespread in media such as television, movies, books, and the internet, it is not always common in relationships and is infrequent in therapy, he posits that maybe it should be.

“the barriers for therapists are their own personal history. Their own associations of shame around sex and sexuality.....that would be the biggest barrier” Pt. H

According to Elliott (1990), clinicians are considerably more likely to have experienced sexual and/or physical abuse than other professionals (Jones, 1998).

3.2 The Irish Therapist – Experiences/Fears

How therapists handle the subject of sex can either open the discussion or close it. An environment of safety can be created by the therapist's open-minded, non-judgmental, and affirmative approach to discussing sexual topics (Love & Faber, 2017).

“it’s the therapists that they go to...a lot of therapists and this is just my experience, they’re of older profile.....so there are cultural challenges, there are age challenges” Pt. O

*“I think it’s a big thing with therapists, they’re afraid to chase it up...ask the hard questions”
Pt. L*

“worry about saying the wrong thing, when people disclose, obviously protocols are in place.. guards and stuff and that can be very daunting and also the energy in the room when you’re talking about something so huge and so horrific nearly envelopes you sometimes....Pt. C

“A huge fear element. A fear of it, because it is something that has to be reported... we have to go through this process with it.. You have to go and deal with guards...you have to deal with Tusla” Pt. S

“The ability to sit in discomfort, sometimes its uncomfortable....its a heavy topic...you got to know your limits, if you are sitting there struggling, you’ve got to refer. It’s an artform” Pt. Y.

3.3 The Irish Therapist - Needs to be more openminded – beliefs/bias

Bias on the part of the counsellor may result in incorrect diagnoses, poor treatment, or even exacerbation of the client's problems. It has been established that bias in the counselling process has detrimental effects (Morrow & Diedan, 1992).

“My biggest problem with therapists in Ireland, is most of them haven’t done enough work on themselves at all” Pt. L

“we have supervision... but we still hold our own judgments and we need to be able to be a bit more openminded about what our judgements are” Pt. C

“he experienced horrific CSA by his mother and he kind of blocked it out..... he began to have flashbacks....went to a counsellor and said that he was sexually abused by his mother and the counsellor said, ‘Mothers don’t do that to their sons’, so he left and never went back to therapy until he was in his 30s” Pt. C

When a client discloses sexual assault, many counsellors are appalled (Courtois, 1988; Knight, 1997; Jones, 1998)

“I have met therapists and supervisors who have just got that look on their face...when you start talking about this stuff which is a resistant look” Pt. H

“judgements and views...without realising they have their own views of what’s normal sex, what’s normal sexuality.... people sense it, they know.....your micro-expressions on people’s face” Pt. C

“You get people that go, ‘Oh, my God, that is horrific’ and you get people who physically shrink back.... people’s minds can comprehend that that could be done to a child” Pt. S

Theme 4 - The Irish Training

All participants voiced their concerns about the lack of training in Ireland on CSA and sexuality in their primary and masters degrees with some optioning for specialised training or going abroad for further training.

4.1 Gap in the Training

Past studies have demonstrated a strong and favourable correlation between the level of training in sexual issues and sexual intervention self-efficacy and the degree to which therapists discuss this subject with clients and their comfort doing so. (Byers, 2011; Miller, 2008), (Love & Faber, 2017)

“I don’t know does it even come up in most trainings...did I do anything on sexual empowerment? No. That’s actually the important bit, is the other side of it” Pt. Y

“a lot of therapists are not equipped. The training is absolutely shite in this country....the trainings are not covering it effectively....I think it absolutely needs to be delved into very deeply” Pt. L

“there’s such a void there in terms of information... training, it’s like a massive area....we don’t have degrees in sexology... no degrees in psychosexual training....they are not trained in sex education or sexuality or sex positivity...the empowerment piece....we need much diverse training, much broader training” Pt. O

“You can’t study sex therapy in Ireland. There is nowhere to study it...I really think the training in sex education with child abuse should be mandatory across the colleges. It should be at least minimum one module” Pt. S

“I think all therapists should receive training in it. I did. That’s a given. That’s a basic. But training is crucial” Pt. H

“I have finished two degrees and there was zero talk of child abuse anywhere through college. It is something that it should be standard practice” Pt. C

4.2 Specialised Training

Two participants disclosed different experiences of attending training at the Rape Crisis Centre (RCC). The RCC provides counselling, training and accompanying services to people who have experienced sexual assault, rape or CSA (Dublin Rape Crisis Centre, 2023).

“I would have went and did training with the Rape Crisis and come away going, okay is that it?...I think there is a gap in the training....a gap in the understanding of sexual abuse” Pt. Y

“I did the training for the Rape Crisis Centre, and I was only a volunteer, it was amazing, it was excellent training, three months” Pt. C

Another spoke about using EMDR as a treatment for CSA;

“the best one I ever went on was my EMDR training....it wasn't a course for sexual abuse as such, but it was a treatment for it” Pt. L

One participant went to UK for psychosexual training;

“Most therapists are going to the UK, I've gone to the UK for some of my training because its just not available here, so that's a huge barrier” Pt. O

Theme 5 – Meaning Making

The participants were asked if reclaiming sexual empowerment is meaningful to clients. They all responded with “absolutely” and shared how they thought it was meaningful. "Meaning making" refers to the active process of transformation or reconstruction of inner global perceptions (Joseph & Lindley, 2005; Park & Ali, 2006; Vilenica, Shakespeare-Finch & Obst, 2013).

“Absolutely... it really was life changing....its about growth.....its reclaiming all round, that empowerment....in somebody asking for what they need....its wonderful” Pt. Y

“Absolutely...I think working through it in therapy is essential to have a happy fulfilling life” Pt. L

“yeah, absolutely....empowering piece, is having intimacy, sensation, pleasure, eroticism for yourself, with yourself and with a partner but not for them...so that's huge” Pt.O

However, Pt. O also shared their difference in terminology around the word “reclaiming”;

“I know you use the term “reclaim” and I love that word but on the other hand, I often feel that it’s not that they are reclaiming something, because they never actually had it...its more that they are finding it for the first time” Pt. O

“Yes, it’s absolutely important...if they can reclaim a joy and a pleasure and a connection with themselves around sex and sexuality after experiencing sexual abuse, sure that’s everything. That’s huge. If they’re given a safe space and they feel safe and comfortable then all things are possible. A light is shone in dark places” Pt. H

“Absolutely, yeah... no matter what model you’re using in therapy it’s always going to come back to relationship and connection and being heard....then the magic happens you know” Pt. C.”

Discussion

The findings provided rich insight into the barriers Irish therapists experience when working with sexually abused clients on reclaiming sexual empowerment. Only a small number of authors have written directly about the challenges faced by counsellors working with this demographic, despite the possibility that counsellors will encounter sexual abuse survivors (Knight, 1997; Lindy, Wilson, & Raphael, 1994; Parisien & Long, 1994; Pearlman & Saakvitne, 1995b; Jones et al, 1998).

Although this author struggled to find literature on reclaiming sexual empowerment in adult survivors of CSA, the outcomes of the findings are consistent with the opinion of Maltz (1995b) in relation to sexual healing. Sexual healing frequently entails a deeper understanding of what occurred and how it affected sexuality, changing sexual attitudes to value healthy sexuality, and developing a deeper understanding of what happened (Maltz, 1995b). Developing a positive sexual self-concept, quitting harmful sexual behaviours, coping with unpleasant reactions to touch, and learning new skills for experiencing touch and sexual sharing in safe, life-affirming ways are all common components of sexual healing (Maltz, 1995b).

Participants raised the issue of clients not feeling comfortable to talk about sex in therapy. According to empirical literature, sexual content is one of the most frequently discussed subjects of nondisclosure (Farber & Hall, 2002; Hill et al., 1993; Martin, 2006; Pope & Tabachnick, 1994; Love & Faber, 2017). Although they are aware of the significance of sexual difficulties in their life, clients in psychotherapy frequently find themselves reluctant or

unable to adequately express their ideas and feelings regarding these matters (Farber & Hall, 2002; Hill et al., 1993; Martin, 2006; Pope & Tabachnick, 1994; Love & Faber, 2017).

The discussion of sexual themes by clients can be difficult for therapists as noted by all participants. Their discomfort with these issues, which is frequently accompanied by a lack of adequate clinical training regarding sexual topics, may lead to avoidance behaviour that manifests as implicit signals to their clients that sexual matters simply don't need to be discussed in therapy to any great extent (Love & Faber, 2017). The specifics of the abuse, particularly those involving violent, sadistic, or unpleasant acts, are much more horrifying. It follows that the aspects of sexual abuse that survivors need to express and process the most, are also the ones that make the counsellor feel the most uncomfortable (Jones et al, 1998). Although asking directly about the abuse can be stressful for many survivors, doing so is a necessary step in treatment because it breaks the cycle of denial and secrecy and allows for a discussion about the unpleasant feelings of shame and guilt that followed the abuse (MacIntosh et al., 2020; Gewirtz-Meydana & Ofir-Lavee, 2021). The intricate relationships between CSA and sexual health highlight the value of open dialogue between therapist and survivor to determine the solutions that are most suited to their needs and unique experiences. (Bigras, Vaillancourt-Morel , Nolin & Bergeron, 2020).

Another concern for participants was the bias and judgements of therapists working with CSA survivors. Morrow & Diedan, (1992) claim, bias on the part of the counsellor may result in incorrect diagnoses, poor treatment, or even exacerbation of the client's problems. It has been established that bias in the counselling process has detrimental effects (Morrow & Diedan, 1992). They argue counsellors will be less susceptible to being influenced by inferential bias if they continuously check knowledge of their biases and work to lessen their vulnerability to prejudice during the counselling process (Morrow & Diedan, 1992).

One participant shared how people find CSA hard to comprehend. However, Vilenica, Shakespeare-Finch & Obst, (2013) look at it from the egocentric nature of childhood makes it simple to comprehend how intense feelings of shame and blame for abuse become internalized, as well as why the coping mechanisms of dissociation and avoidance become heavily relied upon to maintain the integrity of the personality structure (Vilenica, Shakespeare-Finch & Obst, 2013) To properly address the wide-ranging impacts of sexual abuse, counsellors must not only obtain specialized education, training, and supervision, but they must also become conscious of their own reactions while working with this population (Jones et all, 1998).

Another participant shared how one counsellor negatively reacted to a client's disclosure and the long term impact of that for the client. Jones et al, (1998) acknowledge counsellors who work with clients who have experienced trauma from child sexual abuse have unique challenges or reactions. These reactions may jeopardize the client's welfare through a breakdown in the therapeutic alliance, denial or avoidance of the client's history of abuse, or a loss of boundaries between the counsellor and the client (Jones et al, 1998). Compared to clients who have encountered other types of trauma, clients who have survived CSA tend to elicit more personal responses from therapists (Failer, 1993; Jones et al, 1998). According to Lindy et al. 1994 and Pearlman & Saakvitne, 1995b, CSA causes counsellor reactions that are unique to the sexual abuse itself. These responses depend on the client, the counsellor, the treatment model, and their worldviews. They alter counsellor reactions, which can have an adverse effect on treatment success and possibly cause client harm (as cited in Jones et al, 1998). MacIntosh, Vaillancourt, Morel, and Bergeron (2020), warn therapist may unintentionally validate the negative internal working models that emerged after the abuse regarding the self (e.g., You are to blame for the abuse, sex is taboo, etc.) by failing to ask direct questions about the abuse or about sexual functioning. (Gewirtz-Meydana & Ofir-Lavee, 2021)

All participants stated they believed reclaiming sexual empowerment is important and meaningful for clients. This is consistent with Bogar & Hulse-Killacky, (2006); Vilenica, Shakespeare-Finch & Obst, (2013), stating both genders have cited changing one's perspective on oneself as being crucial to recovering from CSA, modifying outdated self-perceptions, acknowledging and connecting with the CSA's impact on their life and sense of self, and letting go of previous self-beliefs. For meaningful change to happen, both the therapist and the client must be aware that this process requires time, effort, patience, and most importantly, compassion. (Vilenica, Shakespeare-Finch & Obst, 2013).

The lack of training was noted by all participants as a huge barrier for working with survivors of CSA. This is also well documented in the literature. While most therapists report some formal exposure during graduate school and an internship, this training is frequently shallow and focuses more on sexual difficulties than good sexual functioning (Byers, 2011). But this has immediate clinical ramifications for how comfortable and capable therapists are to treat sexual content (Love & Faber, 2017). Pearlman & Saakvitne, (1995b) suggest graduate programs should teach student therapists how to react professionally when working with sexual abuse survivors. Working in a supportive therapeutic partnership that fosters acceptance

and non-judgement can give clients the safety they need to examine complex, frequently contradictory belief systems that change may happen. (Vilenica, Shakespeare-Finch & Obst, 2013).

Recommendations/Implications for clinical practice

The topics of CSA, sexuality and sexual empowerment needs to be addressed in primary degrees; This is consistent with Jones et al, (1998) who argue, too frequently, mental health professionals lack the knowledge and training necessary to effectively engage with trauma survivors in general, much less those who have experienced CSA. This emphasizes the value of pursuing ongoing education to ensure that therapists are as knowledgeable and current as feasible. (Love & Faber, 2017).

Participants raised concerns about therapists being uncomfortable to talk about sex/CSA. The idea of being more direct and active in therapy sessions can be intimidating for therapists who have not received extensive training in sex, gender, and sexuality (Love & Faber, 2017). This is especially true when they encounter discussions about gender and sexual identity in contemporary culture, which are receiving more and more attention and significance from younger clients (Love & Faber, 2017). Love & Faber (2017) stress increased exposure to didactics, supervision, and routine discussion can help therapists feel more competent to work through these areas with their clients.

Participants spoke about therapists needing to know their limits and to refer on when they cannot hold the client; An effective counsellor is one who works with clients to generate a positive outcome or change in the clients' view or experience of themselves, or a reduction in unfavourable symptoms (cited in Wheeler 2000). In the end, only the impact on clients throughout the working relationship may determine a practitioner's competency, but it is the duty of training organizations and counsellor trainers to be the profession's gatekeepers. (Mcloed 1992; Wheeler 1996; cited in Wheeler 2000).

Throughout the therapeutic relationship it is the impact on the client that determines the practitioner's competency. This is consistent with the findings from Ullman & Townsend, (2008), they found several approaches to working with survivors described by clinician's,

including feminist, empowerment, client-centred, problem-oriented, crisis intervention, psychodynamic, crisis counselling, trauma treatment, and no specific treatment model were all used frequently. This fits within the pluralistic philosophy developed Cooper and McLeod, whom propose there is no one, right way of doing counselling and psychotherapy as no one theory that fits for clients (McLeod, 2018). They suggest therapists create and develop an integrative approach to therapy that builds on existing models of therapy, which would suit the needs of different clients, at different times, but favouring no particular model over another (McLeod, 2018).

Limitations

The sample size of this research can be seen as a limitation, as well as the interviews being subjective, as they are the experiences of the therapists recalling the survivors' stories. While there is no set standard for IPA sample size, Smith et al. (2009) claim that it is more difficult to conduct a study with a sample size that is "too large" than one that is "too small" however O'Mullan (2019) found a sample of 10 women successfully reflected group patterns of resemblance while acknowledging the unique characteristics of individual lives.

Most of the literature refers to female survivors and only female therapists presented to take part in the interviews. Unfortunately, not having a male voice in the interviews is a limitation of this research. The gender disparity in the literature is also a limitation as males are under-represented across the articles. Bigras, Vaillancourt-Morel, Nolin & Bergeron (2020) state recent assessments ignored the reality of male CSA survivors and instead concentrated only on women's sexuality, the stark gender inequalities underline how urgently men must be included in study processes (Bigras, Vaillancourt-Morel, Nolin & Bergeron, 2020).

A strength of this research is three of the six participants disclosed being survivors of CSA, giving rich insight from both aspects of survivor and therapist combined.

Conclusion

The findings highlight an important gap in the body of knowledge and the demand for further thorough research, on adult survivors of CSA reclaiming sexual empowerment. This

study lays the groundwork for further investigation into the barriers of reclaiming sexual empowerment in an Irish therapeutic environment. There is a critical need for more study that focuses on the recovery from CSA, to include male survivors, as the majority of previous studies have concentrated on female survivors. Therapists who have had success working with this population could make the most evident contributions to this research. The field of mental health would benefit significantly from practitioner-conducted research that outlines the benefits and drawbacks of various treatment modalities in helping clients reclaim their sexual empowerment after surviving CSA.

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This research is dedicated to my Grand Aunt Peggy, who endured horrific familial CSA, she came from a generation of not talking about it and died from vaginal cancer.

“May my ancestors of CSA be at peace from their unspoken wounds”.

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